

Project communication and dissemination strategy

Deliverable D6.1

16 November 2020

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eLTER PLUS

**European long-term ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological
systems research infrastructure PLUS**

Prepared under contract from the European Commission

Grant agreement No. 871128
EU Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation action

Project acronym: **eLTER PLUS**
Project full title: **European long-term ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological systems research infrastructure PLUS**
Start of the project: Feb 2020
Duration: 60 months
Project coordinator: Professor Jaana Bäck
University of Helsinki, Finland
<https://www.lter-europe.net/projects/elter-plus>

Deliverable title: Project communication and dissemination strategy
Deliverable n°: D6.1
Nature of the deliverable: Report
Dissemination level: Public

WP responsible: WP6
Lead beneficiary: Pensoft

Citation: Demirova, I., Metodiev, T. & Barov, B. (2020). *Project communication and dissemination strategy*. Deliverable D6.1 EU Horizon 2020 eLTER PLUS Project, Grant agreement No. 871128.

Due date of deliverable: Month 9
Actual submission date: Month 10

Deliverable status:

Version	Status	Date	Author(s)
1.0	Draft	05 October 2020	Iliyana Demirova Pensoft
1.1	Draft	22 October 2020	Teodor Metodiev, Boris Barov Pensoft
1.2	Review	5 November 2020	GET members
1.3	Final	13 November 2020	Iliyana Demirova, Teodor Metodiev & Boris Barov Pensoft

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Preface

Communication and dissemination are a key function of the future eLTER RI developed and prepared through the eLTER PLUS project and its measures to maximise impact and ensure sustainable and long-term knowledge exchange. This general communication plan has been developed during the starting phase of the eLTER PLUS project by WP6 to ensure the clear definition of, and interactions between, objectives, target groups and suitable messages. A detailed Implementation plan at the end of this document outlines the main activities and frequency of recurring dissemination and communication efforts for each year of the project duration.

Summary

Communication forms an integral part in the development of the eLTER RI, it is a tool for branding and credibility, targeted to user engagement at the highest possible level. Towards this aim, communication takes a central role within eLTER PLUS Advanced community project as a means of ensuring dissemination and uptake of results at every stage during the project lifetime and beyond. The project's Communication plan has been developed to define objectives, target groups and key messages that will guide activities during the project and secure their uptake and further development beyond the project lifetime. The main communication and dissemination tools (website, press releases, newsletters, posters, brochures, social media, videos, meetings, workshops, summer schools, trainings, scientific publications etc.) and social media accounts (Twitter, Facebook) are listed in this document, and the relationship between tools and the different target groups is explained, alongside suggested indicators for actively monitoring their effectiveness. The strategy guides the communication and dissemination efforts to target various audiences and convey clear, understandable, coordinated and effective messages, thus raising awareness and maximising the benefits resulting from eLTER PLUS.

A detailed Implementation plan at the end of this document outlines the main activities and frequency of recurring dissemination and communication efforts for each year of the project duration. Main deliverables and project results are identified with their potential target audiences and clear plans for their successful dissemination and communication to their potential users and where applicable society at large. Major events and external initiatives and projects' websites where eLTER PLUS results can be further disseminated are defined. Frequency of recurring dissemination efforts such as newsletters, news items, social media engagement are set, together with baseline KPIs designed for an ongoing monitoring of their success.

This document is based and builds on the preliminary Project communication plan (Milestone 14, submitted to Coordination in Month 3). Additionally, the target audience definition is informed by the ongoing stakeholder mapping activities conducted in the eLTER PPP project (final version of the stakeholder mapping due in Month 12 as part of D7.1 Stakeholder landscape analysis report).

Introduction & structure

Communication efforts within eLTER PLUS will branch out mainly in two directions, namely raising awareness and engaging the target expert communities in the co-development of knowledge to contribute to the project's goals and objectives (Dissemination), on the one hand, and to the strategic and targeted measures for popularisation and visibility to the wider public (Communication), on the other.

The strategy is developed around five main questions related to:

1. Scope and objectives (Why?)
2. Target groups and stakeholder integration (Who?)
3. Key outputs to communicate (What?)
4. Communication channels and methods (How?)
5. Implementation plan for delivering successful communication (When?)

As a guiding principle, eLTER PLUS Communication will apply a combination of PUSH, PULL and INTERACTIVE communication strategies and channels both in internal and external communication, where specific attention will be put in increasing the share of PULL and INTERACTIVE, as opposed to the more traditional PUSH communication activities. This trend will give users and partners the empowerment to choose and filter their preferred channels and information.

This strategy and plan will target the relevant stakeholder groups in key sectors and define the most appropriate methods to tailor materials and communicate results to: (i) INTERNAL: Site and Platform Coordinators (SPCs), National Coordinators (NCs), Beneficiaries (at managerial and operational level); (ii) RESEARCH: researchers, young researchers, research institutions, research networks; (iii) POLICY: governmental bodies, environment agencies, Directorates-General (DGs) and European agencies; (iv) INDUSTRY: Natural resource users and private sector including national and EU-level associations; (v) PEERS: environmental research infrastructures and monitoring and observations networks and organisations; (vi) CIVIL SOCIETY: NGOs, citizen scientists and lay persons.

This strategy represents a concise plan to guide the communication and dissemination efforts to target the various audiences, spread out clear, understandable, coordinated and effective messages and engage in a multidirectional knowledge transfer to ensure information exchange and interactivity. The strategy will ultimately raise awareness and maximise the benefits resulting from eLTER PLUS as part of the overarching framework preparing the road for implementation of the eLTER RI. This document outlines in detail the communication and dissemination activities, their motivation and implementation.

1. Scope and objectives

The eLTER PLUS communication and dissemination strategy and implementation plan will be of foremost importance for the project's success. Its main objective is to identify and organise the dissemination activities, in order to reach out to the widest possible range of stakeholders and users and to promote further exploitation of the project results, i.e. the implementation of the eLTER RI.

To ensure that these aims are met professionally, effectively and in a timely manner, the following ten basic principles are adopted as communication backbone:

1. Introduction and preference of PULL (upload of materials in Media centre, blog posts and relevant content on website) communication strategies to ensure a PUSH – PULL communication balance.
2. Open access to eLTER PLUS results to the greatest extent possible, while considering intellectual property rights (IPR);
3. Multi-targeted dissemination of results, based on identifying and profiling all relevant target groups;
4. Tailored and targeted communication messages reflecting the needs of each target group;
5. Multivalent modes of dissemination based on traditional (scientific papers, leaflets, posters, fact sheets, policy briefs, press releases, newsletters) and innovative methods (online broadcasting, videos, infographics, blogs, open access journals, data publishing); Extensive use of social networks (Twitter, Facebook);
6. Translating the scientific results, such as best practices, recommendations, policy briefs, etc. into comprehensive and more understandable forms (factsheets, training materials etc.), and when needed into national languages. The scientific language and the methods of dissemination will be adapted according to the needs and specifics (e.g., educational level, different background, different incentives) with the aim to reach various multi-language and multi-cultural target groups;
7. Thorough analysis of project results and definition of communication priorities for each to ensure the strategy fits the concrete needs of the project and its objectives.
8. Widest integration of eLTER results into existing international networks and mechanisms (e.g. ESFRI, ENVRI-Fair), professional organisations, large symposia, and NGO's;
9. Feedback from all stakeholders, including participants in eLTER events used to improve the usability of results and facilitate the work;
10. Sustainability of eLTER results ensured after the funding window by integrating the project webpages and results within the overall eLTER website.

2. Target groups

The broad stakeholder groups within eLTER PLUS were identified during the first phase of the project and through preliminary stakeholder exercises held during the eLTER PLUS & PPP kick-off meetings in March/April 2020. This preliminary analysis served as the basis of the target group identification presented in the preliminary communication plan within Milestone 14 (submitted in Month 3). Since then a detailed stakeholder mapping exercise for the eLTER RI and eLTER as a whole has been designed and conducted as part of the eLTER PPP project Deliverable 7.1 Stakeholder analysis report (Due in Month 12). The target audiences defined below (Table 1) are based on the progress of this stakeholder mapping exercise, while also taking into account the specific needs of eLTER PLUS as a project.

Table 1. Key audiences and engagement within eLTER PLUS.

Group	Prioritised subgroups for eLTER PLUS	Rationale for engagement
INTERNAL	1. National coordinators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Provide relevant information to NCs as ambassadors of eLTER in their national communities and funders. ● Create a sense of community and inspiring incentives. ● Stimulate advocacy at national level.
	2. Site and Platform Coordinators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Offer communication incentives and access to communication tools to promote participation, sense of community and belonging. ● Strengthen the community and increase capacity to engage and collaborate across sites. ● Provide training opportunities for capacity building (WP5).
	3. Beneficiaries (at managerial and operational level)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Provide added value to participating institutions about their participation in eLTER PLUS. ● Stimulate co-promotion and exchange of news.
RESEARCH & SCIENCE	1. Researchers, university students (individuals, teams)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Actively engage the scientific community as main user groups of the future eLTER RI. ● Inform and engage the scientific community early-on on the TA & RA project calls and VA opportunities for participation and uptake (WP7).

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Provide training opportunities for capacity building (WP5).
	2. Research performing organisations (RPOs) and universities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Promote exchange and collaboration of scientific communities. ● Stimulate co-promotion and exchange of news.
	3. Research networks <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Thematic networks (e.g. Mountain Research Initiative (MRI), ILTER, ALTER-Net, Drought-Net, Interact) b. Disciplinary research networks (e.g. critical zone research, biodiversity, hydrology) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Promote exchange and collaboration of scientific communities. ● Stimulate co-promotion and exchange of news.
GOVERNMENT & POLICY DECISION-MAKERS	1. National policy makers (e.g. ministries & their institutions, dedicated committees (e.g. biodiversity) & agencies (environment, conservation))	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Communicate the importance and relevance of eLTER on a national level through eLTER PLUS generated success stories based e.g. on the project case studies and experiences from TA/VA provision. ● Stimulate support and endorsement. ● Engage in activities to improve the national monitoring and verification systems for environmental impacts
	2. European policy makers and European agencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Communicate the importance, relevance and success stories of eLTER and large RIs in general on the EU level.
BUSINESS & INDUSTRY	1. Natural resource users (e.g. mining, forestry, water and agriculture, inshore & coastal fishing, rural tourism)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Demonstrate the importance of long-term environmental monitoring in the management and maintenance of ecosystems. ● Engage with NGOs in advocacy around the positive effects of environmental monitoring.

	2. Landscape and spatial planners and environmental consultants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Drive usage of data from the private sector by demonstrating possible use-cases of the eLTER RI.
PEERS IN ENVIRONMENTAL RESEARCH	1. Environmental Research Infrastructures (RIs in mainly in the ESFRI context)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exchange information on progress and services offered by different RIs, look for points of collaboration in operations, co-design of services, co-location to obtain added value. • Stimulate co-promotion and exchange of news.
	2. Monitoring and observation networks and organisations in-situ and remote (UNECE-Working Group on Effects, WMO, JRC, ESA/Copernicus, EIONET)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide information on the possible uses of the eLTER RI and opportunities for participation in the PLUS TA. • Stimulate co-promotion and exchange of news.
LTSER TARGET GROUPS, CIVIL SOCIETY & INTERESTED MEMBERS OF THE PUBLIC	1. Environmental NGOs; e.g. WWF, Greenpeace, Nature Conservation Associations, BirdLife, FERN	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stimulate co-promotion and exchange of news. • Drive usage of data by the civil society demonstrating possible use-cases of the eLTER RI.
	2. Farm and forest owners' organisations (e.g. ELO, CEPF, EUSTAFOR, national organisations)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stimulate co-promotion and active knowledge co-creation.
	3. Citizen science initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engage citizen scientists in data collection and advocacy among their interest groups and community.
	4. Associations promoting science and education	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stimulate co-promotion and exchange of news.
	5. Interested lay persons	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communicate the relevance of environmental RIs in the context of ecosystem degradation, climate change and relevant issues (e.g. COVID-19 crisis) to stimulate support and raise awareness.

Within the next steps of the stakeholder identification process, a detailed Customer Relationship Management system (CRM) with GDPR compliant contact lists and prioritisation of contacts which will be further used for the purposes of eLTER PLUS communication and dissemination strategy and concrete campaigns and measures.

2.1 Target groups profiling and messages

a) INTERNAL

Short profile: Project consortium partners and members of the overall eLTER community, such as National Coordinators and Site and Platform Coordinators. These persons are mainly scientists with a different engagement and role in the project and the overall building of the eLTER RI. As community members they have a clear incentive to share positive news and initiatives coming from the project. They are also at least partially directly involved in the delivery and therefore dependent on the successful dissemination of eLTER results (in particular the TA/RA/VA Scheme).

Key messages:

- Stimulating information to demonstrate inclusiveness and their participation in a community that is building something as big as the eLTER RI.
- Internal messages that demonstrate progress and create a sense of pride and contribution.
- Incentives for greater participation and to mobilise their channels to further sharing of news and important updates to maximise dissemination efforts.
- Training opportunities for capacity building

b) RESEARCH & SCIENCE

Short profile: Researchers and groups of researchers, as well as institutions performing research in the areas of ecosystem services, ecosystems observation, ecology, long term ecological research, socio-ecology and related fields, who may be direct or indirect users of scientific findings within eLTER PLUS. This group is also a beneficiary of the eLTER TA/RA/VA scheme where they can obtain funded access to the eLTER Sites and LTSER Platforms. They are also beneficiaries of trainings presented as a result of WP5 work. This group is also a potential direct user of the services offered by the eLTER RI.

Key messages:

- Calls for participation in the eLTER TA/RA/VA scheme.
- Highlights of useful resources offered by the project, e.g. trainings developed within WP5, data resources, publications etc.
- Highlights of relevant services tested under eLTER PLUS that will be part of the eLTER RI and will be of use to researchers, to stimulate their interest and help build a community of users.

c) GOVERNMENT & POLICY DECISION-MAKERS

Short profile:

Policy and decision makers at national and EU level who are working in the area of environmental policy, natural resource management (e.g. water, forests), agriculture, and climate change, etc. This group might be interested in services offered by the eLTER RI that will help inform their policies and strategies based on sound scientific knowledge and results obtained through long-term observation data. This group is important also from a strategic point of view, as potential shareholders of the future eLTER RI are among them.

Key messages:

- Highlights of relevant services tested under eLTER PLUS that will be part of the eLTER RI and will be of use for policy and decision makers, to stimulate their interest and attract them to the eLTER RI to build a community of users.
- Success stories of the project in the form of policy briefs and publications that will build a high profile of the project and the eLTER RI.

d) BUSINESS & INDUSTRY

Short profile: This group consists of business and industry representatives, such as natural resource users and companies specialised in environmental monitoring equipment. Landscape and spatial planners, and other environmental consultants provide interpretation and impact assessment services to decision-makers and business investors. Both groups of business users need long-term observation data and some of the services that will be offered by the eLTER RI. This group is a potential user of eLTER PLUS findings and eLTER RI services, as well as a potential advocate of important developments and updates.

Key messages:

- Highlights of relevant services tested under eLTER PLUS that will be part of the eLTER RI and will be of potential utility to natural resource users, landscape planners and environmental consultants, to stimulate their interest and attract them to the eLTER RI.
- Success stories of the project in the form of factsheets and publications that will build a high profile of the project and the eLTER RI.
- Information about Research & Development co-design opportunities and potential markets for instrumentation (or other products) from the business sector.

e) PEERS IN ENVIRONMENTAL RESEARCH

Short profile: Other members of the ESFRI community, representing Environmental Research Infrastructures and monitoring and observation networks and organisations who are potential peers of the eLTER RI in terms of future collaborations, joint ventures and events.

Key messages:

- Incentives for greater participation and to mobilise their channels to further sharing of news and important updates to maximise dissemination efforts and vice versa.
- Opportunities for co-design of services, participation in joint projects.
- Training opportunities for capacity building.

f) LTSEER TARGET GROUPS, CIVIL SOCIETY & INTERESTED MEMBERS OF THE PUBLIC

Short profile: Interested members of the civil society including NGOs and citizen scientists, who can advocate eLTER messages to their communities, as well as lay persons with natural interests in the area of ecology and environmental protection, who will be interested to learn more on the efforts and different initiatives in this area and the role of long-term earth observations.

Key messages:

- Positive messages about key outcomes and milestones of eLTER PLUS and the development of the eLTER RI with real life examples on their uses.
- Incentives to mobilise networks offered by citizen science associations, environmental NGOs, etc. that will amplify eLTER's message.

2.2 Receiving feedback

Getting to know our target groups and how to effectively formulate messages to address them is only one part of the successful communication process. In order to truly understand an audience, communication must be two-directional. Effective feedback, both positive and negative, is a valuable information source that should be utilised to make improvements in the use of various communication channels. Bearing that in mind, eLTER will modify its actions according to feedback received from users. eLTER will take the following actions to ensure a smooth two-directional communication process:

- Establish a direct contact with potential users at scientific conferences, synthesis workshops and other key events;
- Provide participants with the opportunity to evaluate the different events organised by eLTER (workshops, webinars, etc.);
- Evaluate user experiences of the services and resources provided by eLTER (e.g. TA/RA/VA calls);
- Initiate calls for feedback via questionnaires;
- Provide collaborative creation of documents;
- Open a dedicated feedback section in the quarterly newsletter used to evaluate its contents;
- Evaluate feedback indirectly via user statistics for the website, newsletter and social media.

These actions aim to gather feedback from a user's perspective regarding eLTER services, resources and means of communication, and ultimately improve these based on the user needs and wishes. As the project progresses, more communication channels and services will be made available. Therefore, more means for gathering feedback and ensuring two-directional communication will be developed and implemented.

3. Communication methods and channels

Suitable manners of communication and dissemination will be applied to reach different target groups.

The main channels to be used by eLTER PLUS are listed below, followed by a detailed specification and mapping of the use of each channel towards the different target groups outlined above (Table 2). There is an overlap of some key communication channels, as they will be used for both internal and external target groups (e.g. promotional materials, social media etc.).

1. Communication and dissemination planned to be maintained by eLTER:

Internal communication channels:

- Project web pages
- Project training corner (on the web pages) designed to assist WP5 in training activities
- Publication of the project TA and RA Calls and communication campaigns for each
- Bi-annual internal newsletter highlighting updates and recent developments
- Quarterly newsletter
- Promotional materials: brochures, posters, stickers
- Factsheets highlighting important results of eLTER development
- Social networks: Facebook, Twitter
- Multimedia materials: videos, infographics, live broadcasts
- Press releases
- Events: trainings, workshops, summer schools, press conferences

External communication channels:

- Quarterly newsletter, webpages and other online resources of peer organisations
- Specialised networks and channels (environmental, industry and policy magazines)
- Publications in journals
- Publications of data papers
- Mass media

More information about these channels and the status of some available in D6.2 Project webpages.

Table 2. Channels and methods to engage target audiences within eLTER PLUS.

Group	Prioritised subgroups	Communication channels and methods
INTERNAL	1. National coordinators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Specialised internal newsletters to engage in latest developments and news ● Dedicated resources with key documentation and communication materials
	2. Site and Platform Coordinators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Participation incentives ● Training incentives ● Easy to use visual branding tools and standardised texts ● Specialised newsletter highlighting incentives, putting active sites in the spotlight ● Site labelling process as an incentive ● Highlight participating sites through social media and on the website
	3. Beneficiaries (at managerial and operating level)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Press releases communicated with press officers. ● Newsletter snippets exchange to cross-feature.
RESEARCH & SCIENCE	1. Researchers, university students (individuals, teams)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Quarterly newsletter to share new research and collaboration opportunities; ● Publications in high profile journals; ● Stakeholder participation in workshops for knowledge co-creation, mapping, and to initiate a dialogue and receive feedback ● Press releases and periodical factsheets and targeted handouts for project events; ● Social media to create groups of interest and create a community around the project's aims (Including Research Gate); ● TA/RA/VA Calls highlighting opportunities for researchers to make use of the eLTER Sites and LTSER Platforms. ● Training activities planned in the project (including videos, webinars etc.) ● Research relevant eLTER webpages such as research objectives and findings, library containing publications.

	<p>2. Research performing organisations (RPOs) and universities</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Press releases communicated with press officers. ● Newsletter snippets exchange to cross-feature. ● TA/RA/VA Calls highlighting opportunities for researchers to make use of the eLTER Sites and LTSER Platforms. ● Training activities planned in the project (including videos, webinars etc.)
	<p>3. Research networks</p> <p>a. (e.g. Mountain Research Initiative (MRI), ILTER, ALTER-Net, Drought-Net, Interact)</p> <p>b. Disciplinary research networks: e.g. critical zone research, biodiversity, hydrology</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Press releases communicated with press officers. ● Newsletter snippets exchange to cross-feature. ● TA/RA/VA Calls highlighting opportunities for researchers to make use of the eLTER Sites and LTSER Platforms. ● Training activities planned in the project (including videos, webinars etc.)
<p>GOVERNMENT & POLICY DECISION-MAKERS</p>	<p>1. National policy makers (e.g. ministries & their institutions, dedicated committees (e.g. biodiversity) & agencies (environment, conservation))</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Added value case studies to highlight importance of the RI ● Policy briefs and factsheets to showcase important results tailored for the needs of policy. ● Translation of project materials in relevant local languages.
	<p>2. European policy makers and European agencies</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Posting on relevant websites (e.g. CORDIS, DG Env etc.). ● Engagement and exchange of news with relevant networks and mechanisms (ESFRI, ENVRI). ● Attendance of key events through shared communication to showcase collaboration on EU level (e.g. ENVRI booth at the EGU congresses). ● Policy relevant eLTER web pages containing summaries and materials for policy.

BUSINESS & INDUSTRY	1. Natural resource users (e.g. mining, forestry, water and agriculture, inshore & coastal fishing, rural tourism)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Engaging material: videos, infographics, factsheets. Social media engagement.
	2. Landscape and spatial planners and environmental consultants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Attendance of relevant industry events. Industry specific materials: factsheets, infographics. Social media engagement.
PEERS IN ENVIRONMENTAL RESEARCH	1. Environmental Research Infrastructures (RIs in mainly in the ESFRI context)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Newsletters, webpages and other online resources of peer organisations Social media engagements
	2. Monitoring and observation networks and organisations in-situ and remote (UNECE-Working Group on Effects, WMO, JRC, ESA/Copernicus, EIONET)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Newsletters, webpages and other online resources of peer organisations Specialised networks and channels (environmental, industry and policy magazines) Social media engagements
LTSER TARGET GROUPS, CIVIL SOCIETY & INTERESTED MEMBERS OF THE PUBLIC	1. Environmental NGOs; e.g. WWF, Greenpeace, Nature Conservation Associations, BirdLife, FERN	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Social media engagement. Website blog posts highlighting the relevance of long-term ecosystem research. News and newsletter snippets exchange to cross-feature in citizen science association's outputs.
	2. Farm and forest owners' organisations (e.g. ELO, CEPF, EUSTAFOR, national organisations)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Social media engagement. Website blog posts highlighting the relevance of long-term ecosystem research. Specialised networks and channels (environmental, industry and policy magazines) News and newsletter snippets exchange to cross-feature in citizen science association's outputs.
	3. Citizen science initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Social media engagement.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● News and newsletter snippets exchange to cross-feature in citizen science association's outputs. ● Publication of data papers.
	4. Associations promoting science and education	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Social media engagement. ● Website blog posts highlighting the relevance of long-term ecosystem research. ● Specialised networks and channels (environmental, industry and policy magazines) ● News and newsletter snippets exchange to cross-feature in citizen science association's outputs.
	5. Interested lay persons	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● News items on website. ● Social media engagement. ● Press releases and publications in mass media. ● Videos and infographics.

In addition to mapping the use of each communication channel towards the different target groups outlined above, this chapter also provides a prioritisation of those tools and channels. As part of the eLTER Mercury meeting, which took place in a hybrid format between 13 - 16 October 2020, the session on communication welcomed a total of 26 participants. These participants were presented with the contents of table 2 and asked to evaluate the effectiveness of the use of each channel towards the different target groups and subgroups. The discussions during the session also highlighted some novel communication tools, channels or suggestions, which were not initially included in the table.

With regards to the internal audience, and more specifically the national coordinators subgroup, creating dedicated resources with key documentation and communication materials was seen as a more effective approach compared to the specialised internal newsletter. For site and platform coordinators, participation and training incentives, as well as preparation of easy to use visual branding tools and standardised texts were the highly prioritised communication tools. Dedicating resources to a site and platform forum was a novel suggestion not initially considered. Drafting press releases and communicating them with the respective press officers was evaluated as the more effective approach when addressing the third subgroup, beneficiaries.

With the focus set on the academic audience, TA/RA/VA calls and publications in high profile journals were the two communication tools deemed most effective in the workshop. Moreover, the TA/RA/VA calls were also seen as the most prominent tools for addressing research performing organisations, universities, as well as research networks. This is a clear indicator that sufficient resources and efforts should be put into promoting the research opportunities of the eLTER Sites and LTSE Platforms (for example central positioning on the eLTER

webpage, press release, social media campaigns etc). A novel suggestion was to aim for publications not only in high profile, but also open access journals.

Drafting policy briefs and factsheets to showcase important results tailored for the needs of policy was evaluated as the most effective method for addressing policy makers on a national level. Exchanging news and engaging with relevant networks, as well as attending key events through shared communications were the highly prioritised tools for addressing policy makers on an EU level. Important suggestions concerning the policy group included participation in hearings of relevant topics where eLTER is clearly visible, as well as delivering "policy relevant" information on environmental status and the impact of this status on human well-being to policy makers.

For the business and industry sector, producing engaging material such as videos, infographics and factsheets was seen as the optimal approach to engage natural resource users, as well as landscape and spatial planners and environmental consultants. One prominent suggestion was to make full use of the eLTER site catalogue as an industry specific material.

Creating newsletters, webpages and other online resources of peer organisations was evaluated as the most effective approach in the engagement of peers in environmental research. This was the case for both environmental research infrastructures, as well as monitoring and observation networks and organisations. One highly evaluated new suggestion was to ensure that enough attention is dedicated to participation in meetings, where discussions and person to person communication can be initiated.

Setting the focus on the last target group, the civil society and interested members of the public, social media engagement and website blog posts highlighting the relevance of long-term ecosystem research were the highly prioritised tools for both environmental NGOs and farm and forest owners' organisations. Social media engagement was the predominant method for reaching citizen science initiatives and associations promoting science and education. Videos, infographics and other engaging materials were deemed most effective for the communication with lay persons. Some novel tools and suggestions for engaging the civil society group included the development of a wider spectrum of engaging materials (e.g. podcasts, cartoons and animated videos), impact sheets, as well as the translation of such materials in local languages.

4. Dissemination actors

Within the consortium of partners, WP6 will take the responsibility for coordinating communication and dissemination activities and report the results to the eLTER PLUS coordination team. All partners are expected to take part in the dissemination activities and actively contribute to popularise the project and its outcomes.

4.1 Dissemination leader

Pensoft as the leader of WP6 will be leading dissemination efforts during the lifetime of eLTER PLUS. As the dissemination leader Pensoft will be expected to:

1. Create the visual outlook and user-friendly and informative communication tools according to agreed eLTER branding, together with the coordinating team
2. Coordinate and monitor all dissemination activities.
3. Organise dissemination activities on all project levels.
4. Encourage partners to initiate and to participate.
5. Reach out and establish working contacts with relevant activities.
6. Ensure regular quality content for the various dissemination channels within this strategy.

4.2 Dissemination at all partners level

To ensure the broadest impact and highest level of dissemination, all partners will be actively engaged in the dissemination process by:

1. Use of their own personal and/or institutional networks and websites to promote the project.
2. Take advantage of relevant conferences to present the project results and distribute dissemination materials. For this purpose, person months were allocated to all partners according to the dissemination effort to be done.
3. Providing content to the dissemination team.

The communication within the project consortium will be in English. However, most partners will be communicating to local stakeholders and disseminating project results and conclusions in their native languages. They will be encouraged to produce their own translation of the texts of flyers, newsletters, fact sheets and popular summaries of project results which will be designed by the dissemination leader Pensoft. All dissemination products are collected by Pensoft to an archive with the metadata of the products (tracking of origin, use, forum and date).

5. Implementation plan

5.1 Timing and frequency of delivery of ongoing activities

The following plan outlines baseline activities and frequencies:

- Brochure and poster – once a year or every time substantial new results come out, the project will develop an updated version of the project flyer and poster.
- Press releases – roughly 1 press release per year (this number is a subject to change in accordance with the necessities of the project)
- Event materials (brochures, flyers, posters, application forms, learning materials) – prepared 2 months prior to trainings, conferences and workshops

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- Communication building blocks (templates for posters, presentations, administrative documents, electronic booths, brand manual and other eLTER branding materials) - updated versions will be developed as need arises
 - Electronic newsletter – 1 every quarter
 - Internal newsletters to PIs and National Coordinators – as need arises, minimum 2 per year.
 - News, Events and TA user blogs on the website – as need arises, e.g. minimum 1 per month
 - Social networks activity – minimum 1 post per week
 - Attending conferences (either by having an eLTER presentation, eLTER booth, an eLTER related session or by promoting the eLTER services in some other way (e.g. advertising TA/RA/VA calls) – minimum 5 per year
 - Communication contribution to other WPs (e.g. WP2.2 SFP, WP5 Training, WP7 TA-RA-VA calls etc.) - as need arises
 - Publications in relevant media – minimum 1 per year

5.2 eLTER's online communication channels: expectations and impact

Having a strong online presence is one of the key aspects in the context of project management. However, in order to use the various online communication channels effectively, one must be able to evaluate their impact.

This chapter discusses various tools, practices and indicators that can be used to measure the impact of the online communication tools and channels used by eLTER. The focus will be set on the three main communication channels: the eLTER website, quarterly newsletter and social media. Moreover, a detailed analysis of the pros and cons of the social media channels used by eLTER (Twitter and Facebook) is provided in this chapter.

Measuring impact

The eLTER website can be considered as the main online communication channel. It integrates both eLTER PLUS and eLTER PPP projects and describes the path towards the implementation of the eLTER RI. The traffic towards the website can be monitored by Google Analytics. This service provides information about the types of users visiting the website, performance of the available content, as well as overall views of the website and subpages. The specific indicators are listed in the next subchapter, together with those of the two other main communication channels.

The quarterly eLTER newsletter is circulated via Mailchimp, an easy to use marketing automation platform and email marketing service. Mailchimp provides reports for each campaign including indicators such as total opens and clicks, demographic data, top links clicks and others. Such analysis of previous campaigns allows us to distinguish between more and less successful elements and improve these for future newsletters.

The social media is having a global impact on communication and networking, it is also cost and time efficient, it allows access to information anytime, while also providing the possibility to receive feedback. That is why social media should be fully integrated as part of a project's communication strategy. Each social media channel used by eLTER offers different benefits and can have a potential unique use in the context of communication and dissemination, but they can also have some shortcomings. Table 3 summarises the pros and cons of both social media networks.

Table 3: Comparison of the pros and cons of two social media networks for use in eLTER PLUS

	Specifications	Impact within eLTER PLUS
Twitter	<p>Pros: Short, fast, easy communication; popular and with high number of users; Twitter lists - easy way to follow news and interact; Event back-channelling</p> <p>Cons: Rather limited in space and media sharing; Tweets have a short searchability lifetime</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Generate interest and share on-going news and activities through posts/tweets -Twitter lists: build a community around the project and get relevant news -Conference live stream/post-conference review -Personal messages: Twitter email version
Facebook	<p>Pros: Useful for sharing media (pictures, videos); High number of users; Create events and invite users; Community-like feel</p> <p>Cons: Less professional and used mainly for personal social activities</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Generate interest and share on-going news and activities through posts -Share relevant multimedia (in posts, or as separate albums) -Events creation and promotion: strengthening the sense of community around the project -Create groups to share group messages -Insights: provide useful analytics for the development of the page

Moreover, social media provides free and efficient tools, which allow the user to measure the success of their campaign, but also to detect weaknesses and address them (e.g. by updating their communication strategy). Based on the European Commission's updated guidance on social media for EU funded R&I projects, table 4 gives an overview of the main tools, measurements and practices that can be used to measure the performance of the eLTER PLUS social media profiles on Twitter and Facebook. (EC, 2020).

Table 4: Tools and practices for measuring social media impact

	Twitter	Facebook
Analytical tools	Twitter analytics: this tool measures the impact based on two categories - tweet activity and followers. Tweet activity reveals the top tweets, as well as the number & rate of impressions and engagements for a certain period (the longest period available for analysis is 90 days). On the other hand, Twitter can also display the most active and influential followers (active refers to users who often engage with eLTER PLUS tweets and influential refers to users who have a high number of followers).	Facebook insights: this tool is more limited in the sense that it is unable to display each eLTER PLUS follower individually (it just shows the total number of followers), but it is still a tool with a lot of potential. Facebook insights analyses the flow of page followers, views, likes and actions. The tool can also categorise the audience based on age, gender and nationality. It also provides a separate analysis of posts that were advertised, hence revealing whether paying for advertising is worth.
Criteria	Quantitative & Qualitative: In the case of Twitter, both quantitative and qualitative data analysis can be applied to evaluate the performance of the channel. The quantitative aspect covers factors such as number of clicks, likes, shares, tags, video views, new followers, profile visits, engagement rates etc. The qualitative aspect focuses on the detailed audience. Qualitative methods can also evaluate the types of comments and their tone.	Quantitative: As mentioned above, Facebook insights do not provide detailed data about the page followers, which makes a qualitative user analysis very hard. Because of that, identifying statistical (data page followers, views, reactions and actions) will be prioritised in the eLTER PLUS social media analysis
Monitoring and reporting	One further practice helpful for the evaluation of social media performance is the regular monitoring of the channel. In addition to the frequent updates with relevant content (e.g. during conferences, at least one live update should be tweeted per presentation/session), one should regularly check the inbox for relevant messages. Additionally, reporting on communication and dissemination activities to the EU (by including information about the social media accounts, activities, achievements and impacts) will deliver sufficient feedback helpful for the evaluation of the social media performance.	The practices discussed within the Twitter section apply in the case of Facebook as well. One contrast is the frequency of reporting during key events. Unlike Twitter, Facebook provides the use of unlimited characters in each post. Because of that, posting content should be limited to one post a day, which should provide a recap of the progress in that day. One option to capture key messages for both Facebook and Twitter is the use of live video.

Social-media marketing needs continuity to be effective, but ever-changing to keep the audience interested. Bearing that in mind, the number of social media channels used by eLTER will increase as the project progresses. Some preliminary plans include opening a LinkedIn profile where connections with institutions relevant to eLTER can be established, as well as a YouTube account where videos produced by eLTER can be uploaded and communicated.

Indicators

Identifying specific indicators that best fit the area of research covered by eLTER and keeping track of these provides a constructive measurement of the impact of using online communication channels. Acknowledging the factors listed below could ultimately improve their performance.

Website:

- Number of 'real-time' users: Gives an overview of the current active users on the website. This can be a useful tool to monitor presence during demonstrations or exercises on the website.
- Audience overview: For a certain period (hour/day/week/month), this feature displays the total number of website visitors and pageviews, as well as an overview of new and returning visitors, total number of sessions (periods when users are actively engaged with the website) etc.
- Behaviour: This feature provides data such as the average time spent by users on a given page/subpage, or a total number of subpage views before exiting the website.
- Demographics and interest reports: They allow us to better understand who our users are by revealing their age category and gender. However, not all users may have demographics associated with them, only those who are signed in from their Google Account, which allows to gather information from their settings or activity on Google properties.

Newsletter:

- Deliveries: A number and percentage of the successful and unsuccessful deliveries of a campaign. This feature helps detect inactive users and consequently update the subscribers list.
- Activity: A key feature revealing the total opens of the email, number of times the email has been forwarded, total clicks etc.
- 24-hour performance: Displays the number of opens during a 24-hour interval. This feature enables to determine when the users are most active, so that future campaigns can be circulated at a certain time, allowing to potentially increase the open rate of an email campaign.
- Top links clicked: Generates a list of the most accessed links from an email campaign.
- Subscribers with most opens: Generates a list with the subscribers who interacted the most with the campaign.
- Top locations by opens: Generates a list of the countries where the most active users are accessing the campaign from.

Social media:

- Number of Directorates-General (DG's) following the project: The high number of European Commissions (EC's), DG's and other agencies following eLTER is one of the indicators of strong social media presence.
- Connection with other related projects: Establishing a connection with other projects in the same field could guarantee a flow of viewers from the project's target group. One example in the case of eLTER PLUS is the social media collaboration with ENVRI, ESFRI, LifeWatch, ICOS, etc.
- Influence of the followers: One further factor is the "influence" of the followers – if a certain profile following the project has a high number of followers themselves, it is more likely that the results of the project will reach a wider audience.
- Retweet / Share of the posts: Liking or reacting to a post is certainly a good sign for its performance, but the real indicator is the number of times this post is retweeted on Twitter or shared on Facebook.
- Tags: Being tagged in posts related to the project could significantly increase the received attention. This is relevant on both Facebook and Twitter.
- Use of specific hashtags (Twitter specific): During conferences or similar events, creating a specific hashtag provides an easy way to follow the communication around the event.
- Personal messages: A high number of personal messages corresponds to a strong social media presence and ultimately to a high interest in the project. Regularly monitoring the inbox in both Twitter and Facebook can lead to a contact with key persons/institutions.

Planned future activities

The list below provides an overview of periods where a higher social media activity due to the given eLTER PLUS output or event is expected and ongoing campaigns planned within the project.

- 1) eLTER Site Network Campaign** – featuring one site every two weeks / weekly. For the purposes of this campaign, eLTER Sites and their coordinators were collected via the eLTER site catalogue and placed in a randomised order. The dates for posts on the eLTER Twitter and Facebook profiles were set according to the one post per two weeks schedule for the years 2020, 2021 & 2022, and one post per week for the years 2023 and 2024. (see Annex 1). Coordinators are contacted to provide information and engaging images, this both providing engaging content updates for the social media, while at the same time feeling engaged and part of the wider community.
- 2) Training materials** – as part of the communication team collaboration with WP5 a dedicated training corner will be created and dedicated campaigns will be utilised to popularise these resources internally within the community and externally to the scientific community target groups. As part of these campaigns, dedicated social media threads will be posted.
- 3) TA/RAVA Calls** – each year in September a call for participation in the eLTER PLUS TA/VA/RA Scheme will be posted. Being one of the key activities of eLTER PLUS each call will be accompanied with a dedicated dissemination campaign, also featuring social media postings and updates to stimulate engagement.

- 4) **Scientific publications and data papers** – social media postings will be created and shared every time there is a new eLTER PLUS related publications to popularise it and stimulate the community to view, use and cite these publications in their work.
- 5) **Important project deliverables and milestones** – dedicated social media campaigns will be posted as part of the overall engagement campaigns for all identified important project milestones (see Table 5 in section 5.3).

5.3 Major projects outcomes and dedicated campaigns

The activities outlined below feature an overview of important project outcomes and deliverables and the preliminary planned dissemination activities for those. Additional activities may be planned depending on the specifics of each period and the future development of communication tools and practices as an ongoing process. The preliminary dissemination campaigns will be discussed in advance with the key task leaders and adapted accordingly to their preference for means of communication.

Due Date (in months)	Relative Number in WP	Deliverable title	Lead Beneficiary	Target	Dissemination campaign
12	D3.1	Discussion paper on key standard observation variables	UFZ	RESEARCH, POLICY, PEERS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Summary of the essence on the eLTER website - News item - Newsletter item - News snippets for PEERS newsletters and websites - Social media campaign
24	D11.6	Common tools for data discovery, visualisation and exploitation, specifically of data from WP4 sources and pilots, VA and CS	BSI	RESEARCH	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - News item - Newsletter item - Social media campaign
24	D2.2	SWOT analysis and roadmap on incentivising eLTER Site operators and eLTSER Platform managers	UH	INTERNAL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Internal newsletter - Presentation of incentives at an internal workshop
36	D4.3	Workflow and piloting for retrieval and harmonisation of Remote Sensing data and products	BGU	RESEARCH	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - News item - Newsletter item - Social media campaign

36	D8.1	Report on ecosystem specific stressors	ICETA	RESEARCH, POLICY, PRACTICE, PEERS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - News item - Newsletter item - Policy brief / factsheet - News snippets for PEERS newsletters and websites - Social media campaign
36	D8.2	Key parameters influencing biogeochemical processes	BOKU	RESEARCH, POLICY, PRACTICE, PEERS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - News item - Newsletter item - Policy brief / factsheet - News snippets for PEERS newsletters and websites - Social media campaign
36	D8.3	Impact of drought on the WUE of ecosystems and their resilience	TUC	RESEARCH, POLICY, PRACTICE, PEERS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - News item - Newsletter item - Policy brief / factsheet - Press release - News snippets for PEERS newsletters and websites - Social media campaign
36	D8.4	Report on whole-system, socio-ecological extreme events research needs	BOKU	RESEARCH, PEERS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - News item - Newsletter item - Press release - News snippets for PEERS newsletters and websites - Social media campaign
40	D4.4	Piloting of eLTER specific downstream services contributing to eLTER Standard Observation Variables	CSIC	RESEARCH, POLICY, PRACTICE, PEERS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Publication of a dedicated page on the eLTER website - News item - Newsletter item - Press release published on CORDIS Wire - News snippets for PEERS newsletters and websites - Social media campaign
40	D4.5	Data service portal concept and piloting	UKCEH	RESEARCH, POLICY, PRACTICE, PEERS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Publication of a dedicated page on the eLTER website - News item - Newsletter item - Press release published on CORDIS Wire - News snippets for PEERS newsletters and websites - Social media campaign

45	D1.1	Site categories and pan-European network design	EAA	INTERNAL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - News item - Newsletter item - Social media campaign
48	D1.2	Roadmap for eLTER ICT and service innovation	UKCEH	RESEARCH, POLICY, PRACTICE, PEERS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Publication of a dedicated page on the eLTER website - News item - Newsletter item - Press release published on CORDIS Wire - News snippets for PEERS newsletters and websites - Social media campaign
48	D3.3	Review of international standards and recommendations for standardisation and harmonisation of key standard observation variables	WSL	RESEARCH, PEERS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - News item - Newsletter item - News snippets for PEERS newsletters and websites - Social media campaign
48	D9.1	eLTER network representativeness towards biodiversity pressures and trends	UFZ	RESEARCH, POLICY, PRACTICE, PEERS, CIVIC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - News item - Newsletter item - Press release published on CORDIS Wire - News snippets for PEERS newsletters and websites - Social media campaign
48	D9.2	Piloting of eLTER-ICOS co-operation	SLU	RESEARCH, POLICY, PRACTICE, PEERS, CIVIC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - News item - Newsletter item - Press release published on CORDIS Wire - News snippets for PEERS newsletters and websites - Social media campaign
48	D9.3	The pan-European continental scale terrestrial ecosystem model	FZJ	RESEARCH, POLICY, PRACTICE, PEERS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - News item - Newsletter item - Policy brief / factsheets - Press release published on CORDIS Wire - News snippets for PEERS newsletters and websites - Publications in industry

					/ topical media - Social media campaign
48	D9.4	The eLTER network-scale research addressing European environmental policies	CSIC	RESEARCH, POLICY, PRACTICE, PEERS	- News item - Newsletter item - Policy brief / factsheets - Press release published on CORDIS Wire - News snippets for PEERS newsletters and websites - Publications in industry / topical media - Social media campaign
54	D11.3	Piloting data workflows with the Virtual Lab	UKCEH	RESEARCH, POLICY, PRACTICE, PEERS	- News item - Newsletter item - Policy brief / factsheets - Press release published on CORDIS Wire - News snippets for PEERS newsletters and websites - Publications in industry / topical media - Social media campaign
54	D11.7	Data portals and direct data access services	BSI	RESEARCH, POLICY, PRACTICE, PEERS	- News item - Newsletter item - Policy brief / factsheets - Press release published on CORDIS Wire - News snippets for PEERS newsletters and websites - Publications in industry / topical media - Social media campaign
Ongoing campaigns related to important deliverables & running processes					
8	D7.1	eLTER TA and RA process description	EAA	RESEARCH, PEERS	- Publication of the annual calls on the eLTER website
60	D12.1	TA	EAA		- News item
60	D13.1	RA	EAA		- Newsletter item
					- Short press release published on CORDIS Wire
60	D14.1	VA	UCEH		- News snippets for PEERS newsletters and websites - Blog posts from users

					on the eLTER website - Social media campaign
50	D5.1	Site/platform operators training module report	UH	RESEARCH, PEERS	- Publication of a dedicated eLTER training website corner - News item for new videos - Newsletter items for new videos - Short press release published on CORDIS Wire for the final collection - News snippets for PEERS newsletters and websites for important trainings - Ongoing social media campaign
50	D5.2	Whole system approach training module report	BGU		
50	D5.3	Trans-disciplinary training module report	IIT		
50	D5.4	Continental scale training module report	CNR		
55	D5.5	Videos on training events	PENSOFT		
60	D6.3	Quarterly project newsletter	PENSOFT	RESEARCH, POLICY, PRACTICE, PEERS	- Publication of the newsletter - Social media campaign
60	D6.5	Project policy briefs	PENSOFT	POLICY	- Publication of dedicate eLTER Policy Brief corner on the website - News items for each published policy brief - Press release for final collection - Newsletter contribution - News snippets for PEERS newsletters and websites for important trainings - Ongoing social media campaign - Dedicated email campaign to policy contacts in the eLTER CRM

6. Conclusions

This strategy and implementation plan is the basis of all eLTER PLUS Communication and Dissemination activities. The concrete measures will be further developed as the project develops and new tools are adopted. Separate mini plans will be discussed in detail and implemented for all important eLTER PLUS activities and products.

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Annex 1

For the purposes of this campaign, eLTER Sites and LTSER Platforms and their coordinators were collected via the eLTER site catalogue and placed in a randomised order. The dates for posts on the eLTER Twitter and Facebook profiles were set according to a one post per two weeks schedule for the years 2020, 2021 & 2022, and one post per week for the years 2023 and 2024.

Country	Site	Campaign schedule
Latvia	Reservoir of Riga Hydropower Station on the River Daugava	September 2020
Bulgaria	Belasitsa	October 2020
Israel	Arava Platform (ARV)	October 2020
Sweden	Gårdsjön, IM-site SE04	November 2020
Slovakia	Kralova hola	November 2020
Italy	IT22 - Mar Piccolo of Taranto	December 2020
Sweden	Aneboda, IM-site SE14	December 2020
2021		
Latvia	Randu meadows	January 2021
France	LTSER Zone Atelier Loire	January 2021
United Kingdom	Porton Down	February 2021
Slovenia	Tratice	February 2021
Slovakia	Tatra National Park	March 2021
Hungary	Sikfokut LTER	March 2021
United Kingdom	Sourhope	April 2021
Latvia	River Salaca	April 2021
Austria	LTSER Platform Eisenwurzen (EW)	May 2021
Slovakia	Poloniny National Park LTSER	May 2021
Germany	TERENO - Greifenhagen	June 2021
United Kingdom	Esthwaite Water	June 2021
Austria	ICP_Forests_Austria, Mürzzuschlag (ICP_FO_AU15)	July 2021
Austria	Fuchsenbigl	July 2021
Slovenia	Gameljne	August 2021
Israel	Avdat (AVD)	August 2021
Portugal	LTER Ria de Aveiro	September 2021
France	LTSER Zone Atelier Arc Jurassien	September 2021
Poland	The City of Lodz LTSER	October 2021
Latvia	LTSER Engure	October 2021
Sweden	Erken Laboratory (LTER)	November 2021
France	LTSER Zone Atelier Seine	November 2021
Austria	Rosalia Lehrforst	December 2021
Italy	Appennino settentrionale	December 2021
2022		
Germany	TERENO - Schafstädt	January 2022

United Kingdom	Alice Holt	January 2022
United Kingdom	Whim bog	February 2022
Belgium	Brasschaat - De Inslag	February 2022
Spain	Illas Atlánticas / Pontevedra (ES-SNE)	March 2022
Austria	Mondsee Limnological Institute	March 2022
Finland	Hyytiälä SMEAR II LTER	April 2022
Austria	LTER Zöbelboden	April 2022
Finland	Värriö Research Station (Värriö LTER)	May 2022
France	LTZER Zone Atelier Alpes	May 2022
Slovakia	Tatras - alpine summits	June 2022
Bulgaria	Black Sea	June 2022
Romania	Retezat Biosphere Reserve	July 2022
Austria	WasserCluster Lunz	July 2022
Italy	Delta del Po e Costa Romagnola	August 2022
Czech republic	Lysina & Pluhuv Bor catchments	August 2022
United Kingdom	Windermere	September 2022
Slovakia	Polana Biosphere Reserve (Hukavsky grun)	September 2022
France	LTZER Zone Atelier Brest Iroise	October 2022
Italy	IT04-001-T Monte Rufeno LAZ1	October 2022
United Kingdom	Cairngorms National Park LTER	November 2022
United Kingdom	Loch Leven	November 2022
Germany	Rhine-Main-Observatory	December 2022
United Kingdom	Rothamsted	December 2022
2023		
Italy	Lago Bidighinzu	January 2023
Italy	Montagna di Torricchio	January 2023
Italy	Monumento Naturale Torre Flavia (Roma)	January 2023
United Kingdom	Lower Lough Erne	January 2023
United Kingdom	Lough Neagh	February 2023
Spain	Aigüestortes / Lleida (ES-SNE)	February 2023
Germany	TERENO - Wüstebach	February 2023
Austria+70:2:59	Agricultural Research and Education Centre Raumberg-Gumpenstein	February 2023
Romania	LTZER Neajlov catchment	March 2023
United Kingdom	Cairngorms (ECN site)	March 2023
Slovenia	Postojna-Planina Cave System	March 2023
Romania	Braila Islands	March 2023
Hungary	LTER Fulophaza Site, KISKUN LTER	April 2023
Germany	TERENO - Rollesbroich	April 2023

Germany	National Park Bavarian Forest	April 2023
Germany	AgroScapeLab Quillow (ZALF)	April 2023
Serbia	Velika Morava	May 2023
Germany	TERENO - Selhausen	May 2023
Greece	LTSER Platform Koiliaris Critical Zone Observatory	May 2023
Italy	Lago Maggiore	May 2023
France	LTSER Zone Atelier Environnementale Urbaine	June 2023
United Kingdom	Moor House - Upper Teesdale	June 2023
Belgium	Gontrode - Aelmoeseneie Forest	June 2023
Bulgaria	Sozopol - Black Sea	June 2023
Latvia	Mazsalaca Pine	July 2023
Israel	LTSER Northern Negev	July 2023
Austria	Sonnblick Observatory	July 2023
Sweden	Kindla, IM-site SE15	July 2023
United Kingdom	Yr Wyddfa/Snowdon	August 2023
Italy	Golfo di Trieste	August 2023
France	OZCAR-RI H+ PLOEMEUR - GUIDEL CZO	August 2023
Sweden	Gammtratten, IM-site SE16	August 2023
France	LTSER Zone Atelier Armorique	September 2023
Austria	ICP_Forests_Austria, Murau (ICP_FO_AU16)	September 2023
Spain	Doñana Long-Term Socioecological Research Platform	September 2023
Hungary	Balaton LTSER	September 2023
Slovenia	Podgorski Kras	October 2023
Belgium	Sonian Forest	October 2023
Poland	The Sulejow Reservoir LTER	October 2023
Serbia	Koviljsko-petrovaradinski rit	October 2023
United Kingdom	Plynlimon	November 2023
Germany	TERENO - Gimritz	November 2023
Belgium	Ravels Forest	November 2023
Hungary	KISKUN LTER	November 2023
Belgium	Ichtegem - Wijnendale Forest	December 2023
United Kingdom	North Wyke	December 2023
Sweden	Bergslagen (LTSER platform)	December 2023
Spain	Ordesa y Monte Perdido / Huesca ES	December 2023
2024		
Austria	Stubai (combination of Neustift meadows and Kaserstattalm)	January 2024
Finland	Lammi LTER	January 2024
United Kingdom	Wytham	January 2024
Italy	Renon BOL1	January 2024

Austria	ICP_Forests_Austria, KlausenLeopoldsdorf (ICP_FO_AU09)	February 2024
Bulgaria	Srebarna	February 2024
Austria	LTSER Platform Tyrolean Alps (TA)	February 2024
Sweden	Asa Field-research Infrastructure (LTER)	February 2024
Israel	Park Shaked (PSK), LTSER Northern Negev	March 2024
Germany	TERENO - Wanzleben	March 2024
Portugal	Baixo Sabor LTER	March 2024
United Kingdom	Hillsborough	March 2024
France	LTSER Zone Atelier Antarctique	April 2024
Bulgaria	Petrohan-Ponor	April 2024
Slovakia	Trnava LTSER	April 2024
Slovakia	Jalovecka dolina	April 2024
Slovakia	Kremnicke vrchy Ecological Experimental Station	May 2024
Sweden	Svartberget Field-research Infrastructure (LTER)	May 2024
Portugal	LTsER-Montado	May 2024
France	LTSER Zone Atelier Bassin de la Moselle	May 2024
Spain	Las Tablas de Daimiel National Park	June 2024
France	LTSER Zone Atelier Bassin du Rhône	June 2024
Poland	Brenna	June 2024
Germany	TERENO - Siptenfelde	June 2024
Austria	ICP_Forests_Austria, Unterpullendorf (ICP_FO_AU2)	July 2024
Hungary	Kiskun Restoration Experiments, KISKUN LTER	July 2024
Netherlands	LTSER Dutch Wadden Sea Area	July 2024
Poland	The UNESCO/UNEP Pilica River Demonstration Site	July 2024
Serbia	Tara	August 2024
Germany	TERENO - Friedeburg	August 2024
France	LTSER Zone Atelier Plaine et Val de Sevre	August 2024
Austria	ICP_Forests_Austria, Jochberg (ICP_FO_AU17)	August 2024
Spain	The Arid Iberian South East LTSER Platform	September 2024
Romania	Bucegi-Piatra Craiului National Park	September 2024
France	OZCAR-RI M-TROPICS/BVET, Cameroon	September 2024
Slovenia	Cerknica Lake	September 2024

Germany	TERENO - Bad Lauchstädt	October 2024
Slovakia	Bab	October 2024
Spain	Sierra Nevada / Granada (ESSNE)	October 2024
France	OZCAR-RI OHGE Strengbach Watershed OHGE Observatoire Hydro-Géochimique de l'Environnement	October 2024
Israel	Gilat (GLT), LTSER Northen Negev	November 2024
United Kingdom	Conwy	November 2024
Israel	Ramon (RMN)	November 2024
United Kingdom	Glensaugh	November 2024
Austria	Gesäuse National Park	December 2024
Austria	ICP_Forests_Austria, Mondsee (ICP_FO_AU11)	December 2024
Serbia	Fruška gora	December 2024